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Pedro Noguera-Méndez

Faculty of Economics and Business

Department of Applied Economics, University of Murcia, Murcia, Spain

Email: pedrono@um.es

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2637-9920>

Javier Cifuentes-Faura

Faculty of Economics and Business

Department of Financial Economics and Accounting, University of Murcia, Murcia, Spain

Email: javier.cifuentes@um.es

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6763-8525>

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN ECONOMICS TEACHING: ANALYSING SPANISH UPPER SECONDARY ECONOMICS TEXTBOOKS

Pedro Noguera-Méndez and Javier Cifuentes-Faura. University of Murcia, Spain.

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ABSTRACT

The study of economics involves core issues of sustainable development very relevant to society, such as growth, consumption or wellbeing. Accordingly, its epistemology and teaching contents influence other disciplines, the conception of society and the political agenda. From this perspective, it is strategic that the teaching of economics promotes sustainable development. The aim of this paper is to examine what the subjects of economics and business economics teach about sustainability at the upper secondary education level in Spain, and if they contribute to the acquisition of the key competencies of the education for sustainable development. A content analysis is carried out of both the curriculum and the textbooks to that end. Our results emphasise that the ideas, concepts and values transmitted by the Spanish upper secondary economics textbooks do not adequately promote knowledge about sustainability or the learning of the key competencies.

KEY WORDS

Sustainability; economics education; ethics; education for sustainable development; action competence; textbooks.

INTRODUCTION

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) represents a huge challenge for teachers and learners. ESD is highly demanding, since, according to UNESCO, it must be holistic, transformative, contextual, social, action-oriented, interactive and learner-centred. “What ESD requires is a shift from teaching to learning. It asks for an action-oriented, transformative pedagogy, which supports self-directed learning, participation and collaboration, problem-orientation, inter- and trans-disciplinarity and the linking of formal and informal learning. Only such pedagogical approaches make possible the development of the key competencies needed for promoting sustainable development” (UNESCO, 2017, 6). ESD goes beyond the mere acquisition of knowledge, as it requires a type of learning that involves the construction of action-oriented and transformative knowledge. ESD is not only a reaction to a serious environmental crisis but also the result of the evolution of the educational models of the 21st century, which are described by (Mayer, 1992, 406) with three metaphors: “learning as response acquisition, learning as knowledge acquisition, and learning as knowledge construction.” Nowadays, the constructivist epistemology about knowledge (Schunk, 2012), and more specifically, social constructivism, is the prevailing approach in the sphere of education (European Commission, 2002; Eurydice, 2003; Serrano & Pons, 2011), which is particularly clear in ESD (Armstrong, 2011; González-Salamanca et al., 2020; Kalsoom, 2019; UNESCO, 2017). The preference of ESD for constructivism is based on the shared vision regarding learning processes and objectives (Armstrong, 2011). Learning must be a process of active construction of knowledge and meaning which depends on the learner’s previous knowledge and experience. Learning implies the assimilation and interpretation of the meaning of what has been learned. This process involves the learner to realise how this new knowledge influences, operates or manifests itself and what its consequences are for their life and environment (Schunk, 2012). And this is the main goal of ESD: the acquisition of meaning-centred knowledge and action-oriented skills, in order to “integrate the principles, values, and practices of sustainable development into all aspects of education and learning” (UNESCO, 2005, 6).

Considering the above, it may seem that the main challenges in implementing ESD are related to the learning process. However, there are some deficiencies in the contents of particular school subjects because they still teach conceptions about society, nature, development and wellbeing that have not changed sufficiently in the last century and are

not compatible with sustainability. Sustainable development (SD) is an interdisciplinary area, of which the field of economics is one of its basic dimensions (Jabareen, 2011; Polasky et al., 2019; Shao et al., 2011), that seeks certain skills and knowledge (UNESCO, 2017).

The objective of this work is to examine, from their curriculum and textbooks, what the subjects of economics and business economics teach about sustainability in Spanish high schools, and whether this teaching contributes to the acquisition of key ESD competencies. It will be possible to ascertain whether the ideas conveyed by economics textbooks are consistent with the commitments of curricular sustainability or, on the contrary, are contributing to the *status quo*. The commitments assumed by UNESCO stand out, in particular in the UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD), spanning from 2005 to 2014 (UNESCO, 2005), and the Aichi-Nagoya Declaration on ESD in 2014. Specifically, the Aichi-Nagoya Declaration encourages governments to “review the purposes and values that underpin education, assess the extent to which education policy and curricula are achieving the goals of ESD” and to “reinforce the integration of ESD into education, training, and sustainable development policies.” Additionally, Target 7 of SDG 4 of the 2030 Agenda must be noted, which highlights the role of ESD: “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.”

The central role of economics discipline in SD is firmly established. “Economics, combined with earth system sciences, is crucial for understanding both positive and negative impacts of alternatives and the trade-offs involved. Economics, combined with other social and behavioral sciences, is crucial for understanding how it might be possible to shift human behavior toward achieving sustainable development” (Polasky et al., 2019, 5233). Regarding additional reasons why economics plays such a paramount role in ESD, some authors argue that this discipline occupies a position of superiority or prestige in the social sciences as a whole. In this line of thinking, Paul Samuelson stated that economics is the queen of the social sciences, and Lazear (2000) claimed that economics does not belong to social studies but to physical sciences, due to its statistical methods and techniques. These approaches were strongly criticised (Bunge, 2011; Puehringer, 2016) but the truth is that economics has great visibility due to the social relevance of the issues within its scope, such as growth, production, consumption, wellbeing or resource management. All of these issues are essential aspects of SD (Akenji et al., 2015;

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The influence of the economy is visible in the political agenda and in the high positions held by economists in companies and governments around the world. In summary, the economy occupies a privileged position in the economic and political power structure, and it has the means to disseminate its opinions and analyses, as well as to promote or slow down processes of change. Additionally, it contributes to shaping the perception of citizens on issues as crucial as development, wellbeing and sustainability.

This paper contributes to the goal of ESD. Analysing the approach of the economics teaching plans regarding the environment and sustainability is a necessary step to implement ESD. Although various fields of economics have made decisive contributions to understand SD including Natural Resource Economics, Ecological Economics, Environmental Economics and Development Economics (Polasky et al, 2019), the economics subjects seem to remain immovable to the growing evidence of the impact of human activity on the environment at the most basic levels, including upper secondary school and the first years of university (Green, 2012, 2013; Røpke, 2020). *In this study, we examine whether the Spanish upper secondary teaching of economics holds on to viewpoints that are contradictory and inconsistent with ESD, and inadequate for understanding and acquiring SD key competencies.*

The research on what economics teaches about sustainability in upper secondary education is based on the analysis of the curriculum and the contents of textbooks. *Textbooks reflect the consensus and shared visions of their discipline. According to N.G. Mankiw, author of one of the best-selling economics textbooks in the world, introductory and intermediate courses “should faithfully represent the views shared by the majority of professional economists” (Mankiw, 2020, 216).* “The importance of textbooks is indisputable. States and civil society organisations use them to define which knowledge to pass on to the next generation and which competencies to foster. Textbooks often become a political issue because they reflect a society’s educational canon and the constant negotiation processes that shape it” UNESCO MGIEP (2017, 3). According to Serantes-Pazos and Meira (2016, 162), textbooks are the most used didactic resource in Spain both in primary and secondary education. They are an essential tool for transmitting the contents of the syllabus, and a basic resource to teach and learn practices in which the environmental impact should be taken into account (Wynes & Kimberly, 2017). The learning outcomes are frequently evaluated in relation to the contents of textbooks. In

addition, many teachers believe that the requirements of the curricula are met by following the textbooks. Therefore, the importance given to sustainability in recent years suggests the need to review textbooks and their content on SD. If teachers are expected to teach the concept of sustainability, textbooks must be updated so they can provide the necessary support for teachers and students (Biström & Lundström, 2021).

The section that follows examines the core concepts of this research: environmental sustainability (ES) and key competencies for sustainability. Then, the methodology is explained, and the results of the thematic analysis (TA) carried out are presented. The last section is a discussion on the limitations of economics teaching and some proposals are made to contribute to ESD.

CONCEPTUAL UNDERPINNING: SUSTAINABILITY AND KEY COMPETENCIES FOR SUSTAINABILITY

According to the best-known definition, SD is the ability to ensure that humanity “meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987, 24). Therefore, it requires the integration of economic, social and environmental dimensions. This work focuses on ES, which, as stated by (Goodland, 1995, 6), “seeks to sustain global life-support systems indefinitely.” Following (Vucetich & Nelson, 2010), ES is determined by the relationship between society and nature. This relationship entails a physical dimension (exploitation for the use and enjoyment of nature) and an ethical attitude (understanding ourselves in relation to nature as well as our relationships with other people, other living beings and nature in general). The exploitation of environmental resources and services is affected by technology, the understanding of nature, and the understanding of how this exploitation affects society and nature. However, the relationship between society and nature is also affected by the ethical dimension, that is, by normative issues (for instance, which behaviours are acceptable and which not). This conceptualisation emphasises the normative content of sustainability and the critical nature of ethical attitudes, which determine how we use technologies, what we consider to be a healthy ecosystem and its acceptable level of exploitation (Vucetich & Nelson, 2010). **“Sustainability is a normative notion about the way how humans should act towards nature, and how they are responsible towards one another and future generations” (Baumgärtner & Quaas, 2010a, 445).** 'Sustainability', like other concepts, such as 'development' or 'poverty', contain

'facts' and 'values' that are entangled, and in these cases, 'facts' cannot be understood or evaluated without considering the 'values' (Putnam, 2002).

The diversity of ethical positions with respect to nature explains why there are significant differences, for example, in the perception of the value of a mountain, non-human animals or an ecosystem. In addition to an instrumental value, natural beings and goods have an intrinsic or existential value, regardless of whether they can serve other purposes (Brenan & Lo, 2020): “In that way, acknowledging nature's intrinsic value is practically important because it should influence decision-making processes” (Vucetich et al., 2015, 327). Therefore, ethical positions towards nature matter, as they have an impact on the degree of sustainability of human actions (Foladori, 2007; Gutiérrez & Pozo, 2006; Riechmann, 2005). Human relationships, in the present and in the future, also have relevant normative implications. The notion of ethical universalism (this means intra and intergenerational equity as all human beings have equal value) is a fundamental principle of sustainable human development (Anand & Sen, 2000). Therefore, due to the ethical aspect, we are challenged by nature and by other individuals to maintain a respectful relationship with the environment.

In this normative context, it is common to distinguish between anthropic and non-anthropocentric ethical positions (Goralnik et al., 2014). In the anthropocentric perspective, the human being is the central superior species that stands above the rest and, in its most extreme version, is the only species with intrinsic value (Brenan & Lo, 2020), and the only entity with moral rights (Leyton, 2008). From the non-anthropocentric perspective, the moral community extends to non-human animals (biocentrism) and can also include any element of the natural environment (ecocentrism). In fact, acknowledging the intrinsic value of some aspects of nature, other than the instrumental value, is a step forward in nourishing them and expanding moral rights (Vucetich et al., 2015).

Aldo Leopold, in his essay *The Land Ethic*, pointed out that ‘conservation’, understood as the harmony between humanity and nature, progresses very slowly: “The usual answer to this dilemma is 'more conservation education.' No one will debate this, but is it certain that only the volume of education needs stepping up? Is something lacking in the content as well?” (Leopold, 1949, 207). According to Aldo Leopold, education lacks a land ethic which creates an intimate bond with nature, in the form of values and attitudes that seek harmony and value the existence of landscapes, ecosystems and life. This bond must

imply the understanding that nature is more than a resource. Sustainability must be conceived as a mental state that lies “the notion of a right relationship with nature which both conditions our attitudes towards the environment and our sense of our own identity” (Bonnett, 2002, 9). "Our relationship with nature, whatever its kind, is an important aspect of our own identity and thus of our self-knowledge" (Bonnett, 2002, 14). Education must serve this purpose, as acknowledged by UNESCO (2017), through one of the key competencies for ESD: the normative competency.

The transformative and action-oriented nature of ESD conditions learning processes in a significant manner. Knowledge is not enough anymore: action-oriented skills and competencies are now sought after. In this sense, Jensen & Schnack (1997) emphasise that environmental education must train citizens to act and bring about changes at the individual and social level. The concept of action competence "should occupy a central position in the theory of environmental education" (Jensen & Schnack, 1997, 163).

The Aichi-Nagoya Declaration emphasises the potential of ESD “to empower learners to transform themselves and the society they live in by developing knowledge, skills, attitudes, competencies and values required for addressing global citizenship and local contextual challenges of the present and the future.” The teacher’s main role in the acquisition of competencies must be that of the facilitator of the learning processes: “competencies cannot be taught but have to be developed by the learners themselves. They are acquired during action, on the basis of experience and reflection” (UNESCO, 2017, 10). Competence is associated with being able, and willing, to be a qualified participant (Jensen & Schnack, 1997). Wiek et al. (2011, 204) use the definition of competence as “a functionally linked complex of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable successful task performance and problem solving.” And UNESCO (2017, 10) indicates that “competencies describe the specific attributes individuals need for action and self-organization in various complex contexts and situations.”

It is generally acknowledged that certain key competencies are necessary to guarantee successful educational plans and, in particular, to achieve the demanding objectives of sustainability programmes (UNESCO, 2017; Wiek et al., 2011). Key competencies are multifunctional, transversal and required for all learners, and play a crucial role to advance SD (UNESCO, 2017). According to de Haan (2010), Rieckmann (2012) and Wiek et al. (2011) (as cited in UNESCO, 2017, 10), these key competencies are as

follows: systems thinking competency, normative competency, collaboration competency, critical thinking competency, anticipatory competency, strategic competency, self-awareness competency and integrated problem-solving competency. The first four key competencies are the most relevant ones in this work as they will be connected to the contents of the textbooks analysed. Systems thinking competency entails the capacities and skills for developing a holistic and systemic approach in order to analyse complex systems and understand the relationships between components or variables. Normative competency is necessary to understand the rules and values underlying the actions and to negotiate sustainability values and goals. Collaboration competency requires core skills to interact, collaborate, understand and respect others, as well as finding solutions by using participatory methods. Critical thinking competency is “the ability to question norms, practices and opinions; to reflect on one's values, perceptions and actions; and to take a position in the sustainability discourse” (UNESCO, 2017).

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In Spain, the 2006 education law (LOE) represented the introduction of teaching by competences; in 2013, a new educational reform took place (LOMCE), one of the objectives of which was to deepen the learning of key competences, prominently 'know-how' and 'learning to learn'. The Bachillerato curricula, corresponding to the 2013 education law (LOMCE), for the subject of economics has also been taken into account for the qualitative and descriptive analysis of SD in those educational plans, (BOE, 2015). At the end of 2020, a new education law was passed (LOMLOE) which is largely based, according to Medina & Galván (2021) and Caro (2021), on SDG 2030 targets and indicators. It is foreseen that the curriculum, objectives, and organisation of teaching will be modified starting in the 2022-2023 school year.

In Spain the stage of Compulsory Secondary Education (ESO) lasts four years (12-16 years old) and the Bachillerato cycle comprises two years of non-compulsory university-oriented training (16-18 years old). Our work focuses on the analysis of SD teaching in the subjects of economics and business economics (the contents of the curriculum that differentiate each subject can be found in Table 1), which are taught in years 1 and 2 of Bachillerato only for those students who choose to study the Social Sciences branch.

We have analysed the curriculum (BOE, 2015) and twelve Bachillerato-level textbooks. Six textbooks are on the subject of economics, taught in the first year of Bachillerato (Cabrera, 2015; Colino et al., 2015; Gómez et al., 2015; González, 2015; Martínez, 2020; Penalonga, 2019), whereas the others are on business economics, for the second year (Alfaro et al., 2016; Cabrera, 2011; Molina, 2020; Palomino et al., 2009; Torrecillas et al., 2016; Torres & Castillo, 2009). It is a wide sample which includes books distributed by the five most important publishing houses.

Table 1

Blocks of contents established by the Spanish Ministry of Education for the curricula of the subjects of economics and business economics in Bachillerato.

Economics	Business economics
1. Economy and scarcity. The organisation of economic activity	1. Businesses
2. Productive activity	2. Business development
3. The market and the price system	3. Business organisation and management
4. Macroeconomics	4. Productive function
5. Financial aspects of the economy	5. Commercial function
6. The economy's international context	6. Information
7. Economic imbalances and the role of the State in the economy	7. Financial function

Source: Own elaboration from BOE (2015).

A thematic analysis (TA) approach, based on Braun & Clarke (2012, 2021a, 2021b) and Nowell *et al.* (2017) has been performed. The point of departure for the TA (Braun & Clarke, 2012, 2021a, 2021b) of the curriculum and selected textbooks was the conceptual underpinning and the research questions. Sustainability and action-oriented competencies, their elements, and interactions, are the main concepts of this research examined in the previous section. Learning what sustainability means necessarily implies analysing the relationships between society and nature **and considering their normative character**. In addition, we have to determine whether economics textbooks facilitate or, on the contrary, hinder the acquisition of ESD key competencies (UNESCO, 2017). More specifically, the analysis is aimed at determining whether the teaching of economics follows a holistic approach, takes into account the normative content of actions and motivations, fosters action and collaboration to advance SD, and whether it develops critical thinking and a personal viewpoint regarding sustainability.

Therefore, the research questions are aimed at a) determining what concept of SD or sustainability is to be provided as well as its characteristics and dimensions; b) determining whether the analysis of the economic system (institutions, companies and economic activities) takes into consideration its interactions with the environmental system; c) studying the role that ecosystem resources and services play in human well-being; d) examining how textbooks deal with their normative dimension, the ethical attitudes involved in society's relations with nature: the interests of present and future generations and non-human beings; e) examining the degree of depth, criticism and reflection applied to the study of SD, and especially whether and how contradictions, difficulties or dilemmas around sustainability, and the relationships between its dimensions, are considered; and f) regarding SD, determining where and how the systems thinking competency, normative competency, collaboration competency and critical thinking competency are considered.

TA (Braun & Clarke, 2012; Nowell et al., 2017) has been structured in different stages and both deductive and inductive analyses have been applied. First, we analysed the curriculum, the general structure of textbooks and conducted an explicit content search on sustainability and SD. This process included the identification and analysis of the concepts most associated with SD such as economic growth, production, consumption, pollution, climate change, and natural resources. Second, we analysed the location and extent of these explicit contents in the textbooks. Thirdly, these contents were analysed in order to offer an answer to those research questions. This stage includes the examination of the acquisition of the ESD key competences and the identification of latent content. Some economic principles and ideas related to the comprehension of ES and the acquisition of SD key competencies were identified. Fourthly, comparative content analyses were carried out between the books in each speciality as well as between the two specialities. Finally, three themes were derived from the process of analysis and reflection around which the results of the analysis are presented.

It is important to note that this methodology is not limited to the analysis of explicit content, but allows us to consider the meanings and relationships of the latent content in the textbooks, through reflection and the use of related concepts and theories. It is also worth highlighting its differences with respect to the qualitative content analysis methodology. "Although there is no one widely agreed on set of procedures for qualitative content analysis, most authors emphasize the use of a codebook or coding frame (...). In

contrast, reflexive TA does seem to offer the researcher a distinct approach, one that is fully qualitative in terms of both its procedures and the underlying research values” (Braun & Clarke 2021b, 40). Theoretical flexibility and interpretation are two main aspects of the TA undertaken. It requires time and reflection for meanings to be revealed from the explicit and implicit contents and for the themes and ideas to arise (Braun & Clarke, 2021a). We deeply agree with two authors quoted in Braun & Clarke (2021a, 1), who argue that TA demands more conceptual and design thinking than off-the-shelf methodologies (Willig, 2013; McLeod, 2015). “McLeod (2015) described TA as a good choice for researchers who feel confident that they know what they are trying to achieve.” The authors of this work have carried out the reflexive TA of textbooks assuming the need to adopt effective responses to the current environmental crisis. The starting point is a broad review of the literature on SD, the understanding of SD dimensions and ESD key competencies, and the analysis of the concepts that are taught in the subjects of economics and business economics but come into conflict with SD learning and ESD competencies.

RESULTS

In this section we introduce the results of reflexive TA carried out on textbooks selected, which is structured around three core themes. These main themes are: vanishing and marginalization of SD, superficiality and non-criticism, and the resistance of the curriculum and textbooks to change principles and ideas that hinder ESD. The curriculum of ESO and Bachillerato established by the Spanish Ministry of Education (BOE, 2015) reveals the educational context in which the subjects of economics and business economics are integrated, and the reach and role assigned to SD. Table 1 presents the content blocks of the curriculum of both economics and business economics as the basic topics which the textbook elaborates on. For the purposes of this study, it was paramount to determine whether the economics curricula and the textbooks contemplate the analysis of the relationships between the economic system and the environment, the dependence of human well-being on ecosystem resources and services as well as the conflicts, **the normative character of sustainability, and the** difficulties and dilemmas arising from SD. Moreover, we have to clarify if these textbooks promote or restrict the achievement of the key competencies for SD.

Vanishing and marginalisation of SD

The study of sustainability in the curriculum and the textbooks examined is very insufficient, and it occupies a peripheral position in teaching programs. It is a remarkable fact how little attention is paid to SD. This constitutes the first theme that emerges clearly from the analysis. Economics teaching does not consider SD a relevant issue despite the commitments assumed (UNESCO, 2005 and the Aichi-Nagoya Declaration on ESD), the scientific evidence on the severity of climate change, the deterioration of ecosystems and their anthropogenic origin (Carpenter et al., 2006; IPCC 2021; UN Environment 2019), and the central role that the discipline of economics should play in meeting the SD challenge (Polasky et al., 2019). It is surprising that only one sentence in the general provisions (chapter 1) of the curriculum is related to SD: "The curricula of ESO and Bachillerato must include elements that deal with sustainable development and the environment" (BOE, 2015, 174). This contrasts with the space devoted to other cross-curricular topics, such as entrepreneurship, physical activity and nutrition, education in road safety, equality or violence prevention. The term 'sustainability' only appears five times; none of them in the economics curriculum taught in Bachillerato. The term 'sustainable development' is found twenty times; only one of them in the economics curriculum of the first year of Bachillerato. To understand the scope of this, it is necessary to know that the aforementioned curriculum is very extensive (378 pages) and includes 91 school subjects. The attention paid to SD in other subjects, such as geology, geography or physics and chemistry is greater. With these guidelines from the Ministry of Education, only very limited attention to SD can be expected, especially in the economics subjects. It is apparent that the commitments assumed within UNESCO for ESD (UNESCO, 2005) are not properly reflected in these curricula.

Contents related to sustainability have been found only in the last block of the economics curriculum of the first year of Bachillerato: Economic imbalances and the role of the State in the Economy (Table 1). Nature is merely considered as a resource and ethical attitudes are ignored. The environment is considered "as a sensitive and scarce resource", and the reflection on "the impact of growth and cyclical crises in the economy and their effects on the quality of life, the environment and the distribution of wealth at the local and global level" is used as an evaluation criterion. Additionally, there is some information on the

impact of growth on the environment, the potential of SD, and the development of positive environmental attitudes. Finally, environmental goods are described as “a scarce factor of production that provides inputs and collects waste, which makes the assessment of the associated costs necessary.” As to the curriculum of business economics, the environment is even further ignored, as the reference to the terms ‘sustainable’ and ‘sustainability’ is null. However, the environment is mentioned in Block 1: Businesses. It includes the “assessment of the social and environmental responsibility of businesses” in the contents, as well as an evaluation criterion that refers to the social and environmental implications of businesses.

All the economics textbooks for the first year of Bachillerato examined have included some information on economics and the environment at the end of the book. In some cases, there is a whole unit devoted to the analysis of environmental problems and SD (Colino et al., 2015; Martínez, 2020); whereas, in others, there is only one or two sections within the unit dealing with the role of the State and other great problems or challenges (Cabrera, 2015; Gómez et al., 2015). None of the books address SD from the beginning; for instance, in the explanation of the economic system and economic activities. Summarising, we can highlight that the role of SD and sustainability is insufficient, limited and peripheral in the examined economics textbooks.

Superficiality and non-criticism

SD not only occupies a small and marginal space, but it is also addressed superficially. Textbooks do not analyse economics and the environment in an intersectional way, when describing concepts such as consumption, growth, distribution, markets or international trade. In general, the systemic analysis, by which the complexities and interactions between society, economy, and environment, local and global, as well as between the different dimensions of sustainability, is weak or absent. The holistic and critical analysis of the causes and consequences of the deterioration of the environment, as well as its distributional aspects, is also absent. Critical reflection on the concept or definition of sustainability and its dilemmas, and on the production and consumption models as drivers of environmental problems is also very limited or non-existent. If the concept itself is not studied in depth, nor are the normative judgments or values that underlie sustainability. Therefore, the role of collaboration and participation in SD is also ignored, particularly

the participatory analysis and the establishment of consensus on the current values and the necessary changes in ethical attitudes to advance sustainability. These deficiencies are significant, limiting the understanding of the concept, the scope of the problem, and the learning of key competencies; more in particular, the learning of the four key competencies indicated above: systems thinking competency, normative competency, collaboration competency and critical thinking competency. Competencies, according to UNESCO (2017, 10), “are acquired during action, on the basis of experience and reflection”. Apparently, the textbooks analysed do not foster action and therefore do not facilitate this type of learning.

Nevertheless, some of the analysed textbooks highlight the environmental costs of growth or industrial production occasionally (Cabrera, 2015, 53; Colino et al., 2015, 120; González, 2015, 180). The title of the last unit in Gomez et al. (2015) is "Sustainable development: a challenge for the economists of the future," as if SD were solely a problem of the future. Cabrera (2015) uses the title "The great challenges of the current economy," where the author highlights the fact that nature is a provider of services and resources and it is necessary to take measures in the transition towards a green economy: greater energy efficiency, higher ecological taxes or reduced use of carbon-emitting energy sources. Most of the textbooks reviewed include only the usual definition of SD (Brundtland, 1987), despite its anthropocentric character without mentioning that nature is just a resource under such a perspective. Moreover, all the textbooks underline the instrumental value of the ecosystem services only, as established by the curriculum, so there is no mention of the ethical attitudes in SD. On the other hand, Penalonga (2019), which includes a definition of ES (capacity of a system to maintain its diversity, performance and balance over time), is the only textbook that pays attention to the three dimensions of sustainability.

Another outstanding characteristic found in all the books under analysis is the fact that the economic system is presented as a self-sufficient system which works independently of nature. They use the model of the circular flow of income that reflects the monetary and physical exchanges between economic agents: households, companies and public administrations. Therefore, the relationships that the economic system maintains with society and nature are completely ignored.

The paradigm of economic growth being the main policy objective is present in all the textbooks that were examined, even when SD is explained. “Economic growth is one of the common objectives of every society. It implies a greater production of goods and services, which means a greater satisfaction of people's needs; that is, an increase in quality of life and general well-being” (Martínez, 2020, 33). The paradigm of economic growth as society’s main purpose and its limits is not criticised even though its negative effects are usually outlined in the last unit, when explaining depletion of natural resources, pollution and climate change. Martínez (2020) indicates that SD is the economic growth that fosters “improved living conditions in a sustainable way over time (...) The key to SD lies in achieving the sustainability of the economic system of our society (production, distribution and consumption activities), hence enhancing quality of life in the present and the future” (Martínez, 2020, 233). In the same vein, Gómez et al. (2015, 204-205), in the last section of the book (“The Economic Consideration of the Environment: SD”), explain SD by highlighting the fundamental role of economic growth, which may imply some disadvantages such as pollution and depletion of natural resources. Therefore, it is not clearly established that SD should safeguard ES, but rather subordinate ES to the improvement of the quality of life.

When the conflicts of interest are mentioned, they focus on the negative effects that certain measures, such as reducing emissions, may have on production. It is also common to point to innovation and new technologies as the solutions to the current crisis. “The potential climate disaster faces us with a crucial dilemma: should we reduce the current consumption of fossil fuels to combat climate change, even if it implies less economic growth, or, on the contrary, should we wait, trusting that future scientific advances will reverse climate change?” (Cabrera, 2015, 303). The prevailing approach is the status quo (trust on existing policies and innovation), but Martínez (2020, 235) underlines the need for a paradigm shift to achieve sustainability, which must involve all economic agents, including production and consumption.

The analysis of business economics textbooks is aimed at establishing the way that some concepts are explained: interactions with the environmental system, the dependence of businesses and their goals on ecosystem resources and services, and the underlying ethical attitudes. The contents on sustainability are further reduced than in economics textbooks. The model of the circular flow of income and its consequences is explained but the environmental contents are considered in the first block, when the nature, characteristics

and interrelationships of businesses are defined, including its social and environmental relationships. It is apparent that most books introduce concepts related to the environment, but only two (Cabrera, 2011; Palomino et al., 2009) address the concept of sustainability. The rest of the textbooks analysed refer to the impact that business activity has on the environment and the importance of taking measures to protect it. The index of almost all the books includes a heading for the environmental issue, which also appears associated with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) (Alfaro et al., 2016; Torres & Castillo, 2009).

In general terms, the analysed textbooks teach the idea that current policies, investment and innovation will provide the necessary adjustments to achieve SD. As the multidimensional nature of SD is ignored, the relationships or conflicts between economic, social and ES, and between interest groups and generations are not addressed. Economic growth remains a necessary condition of SD, socio-environmental dilemmas of the transition to SD are not tackled, and SD is not explained in relation to consumption, production and globalisation, among others.

Some works on the analysis of secondary school textbooks on Climate Change and environmental contents in Spain make similar criticisms and are aligned with the results obtained in this work. Edwards & Greca (2009) and Navarro-Díaz et al. (2020) highlight that the views provided in these textbooks are biased, fragmented, and reductionist. Serantes-Pazos and Meira (2016) points out that the production and consumption model is not questioned, and neither is its responsibility in the origin of Climate Change. Hernández-Carretero et al. (2018) criticises that the proposals focus on global actions, as opposed to individual actions and responsibilities, and self-criticism is not encouraged. For their part, Serantes-Pazos and Meira (2016) and Navarro-Díaz et al. (2020) highlight, among other limitations, that asymmetries, conflicts, or complex relationships between causes and strategies are not considered, nor is the issue of climate justice addressed. Finally, Serantes-Pazos (2017) and Hernández-Carretero et al. (2018) coincide in pointing out that textbooks do not provide teaching that enables action. Our results are also similar to those found by Biström & Lundström (2021, 286), who highlight the unclear, ‘obscuring’, analysis of the complexity and conflicts of SD in geography and biology textbooks, where “contradictions and complexities regarding achieving SD across multiple dimensions are placed out of focus.”

Given these circumstances, it is unlikely that these textbooks will contribute to the understanding of SD or the acquisition of the key ESD competencies. More specifically, the normative, systems thinking and critical thinking competencies are disregarded because of the following reasons, respectively: the moral and normative dimension of SD is overlooked, the analysis of SD is not holistic, and critical analysis is not included. These shortcomings can be explained not only by the lack of attention paid to SD, but also by limitations with regard to the consolidation of competence-based learning in the Spanish education system. Despite several education reforms that have promoted learning of key competencies, it is recognised that the teaching-learning process in Spain is insufficiently innovative, and that it is still excessively theoretical and rote learning (Hernández-Carretero et al., 2018; Martínez-Losada & García-Barros, 2005).

Resistance to change principles and ideas that hinder ESD

Why has ESD not been incorporated in the teaching of economics? Is the economy subject to additional constraints that make its adaptation difficult? The answers to these questions point to the theoretical and epistemological bases of the economic discipline, whose mainstream approaches maintain some ideas contrary or conflicting with ESD.

The highly similar positions regarding SD in the books analysed is due not only to the poor common guidelines of the curriculum, but also to the fact that the authors probably share a training in the framework of neoclassical economics. This facilitates a general agreement on what to teach but particularly regarding sustainability. As neoclassical economics is the most influential current of economic thought, it is also the approach most taught in universities and textbooks. **Bäuerle (2021, 54) underlines that “Academic economic education reveals an enormous degree of standardization in form and content across institutional and national borders (Graupe 2019). Regarding content, economics textbooks almost exclusively introduce students to a fixed and narrow corpus of theoretical and methodological considerations, mostly identified with neoclassical theory (Fullbrook 2009, 18 f.)”.** Therefore, it can be assumed that the teaching of economics in upper secondary education is conditioned by the programme followed by universities and by the theoretical and epistemological framework of the discipline. Bowles & Carlin (2020) and Røpke (2020), from the analysis of the subject Econ 101 (a standard introductory university course of economics), and (Green, 2013), from interviews with

students, pointed out that the teaching of economics is characterised by its immobility and lack of adaptation and response to criticism, real problems, and new evidence. All these limitations are particularly evident in relation to sustainability.

The criticisms that neoclassical economics has received from other schools of thought or perspectives, such as Ecological economics (Common & Stagl, 2015; Leopold, 1949; Wackernagel & Rees, 1998), Institutionalist and Evolutionary economics (Hodgson, 1993, 1998) or the Post-Autistic economics movement (PAE, 2000; Söderbaum, 2017), are numerous and well known. In relation to SD, several well-established ideas are conflicting and inadequate in the teaching and understanding of SD. Some of these concepts are the idea of economy as a closed system, the paradigm of economic growth and its limited conception of the functions of nature, and the idea of 'weak sustainability' by which 'human capital' and investments can substitute 'natural capital.' Other conflicting concepts are the sectoral perspective, the willingness to build a positive economy that deals only with 'facts' and not with 'values', and the notion of *homo economicus* linked to individualism and personal interest (Mankiw & Taylor, 2020; Martínez-Alier, 1999; Putnam, 2002; Sen, 2003; Wackernagel & Rees, 1998).

From those six inadequate ideas, the most pernicious one is the omission of the interactions between the economy and nature, since ES is not explained nor considered in an intersectional way. The economic system is explained as a self-sufficient closed system, represented by the circular flow of income, and independent of the biosphere (Bowles & Carlin, 2020; Mankiw & Taylor, 2020; Martínez-Alier & Roca, 2015; Röpke, 2020; Wackernagel & Rees, 1998). However, environmental resources and services play a fundamental role in the processes of consumption, production and human well-being (Costanza, 2008; Costanza et al., 1997; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). This omission hampers the understanding of the causes of the environmental crisis since it has been the increasing human pressure in the last century that has caused the deterioration of many ecosystems (IPCC, 2021; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005; Schmelzer, 2015). When considering the economy as an autonomous system, the limits to growth do not exist. Nevertheless, the economy is an open system that interacts with nature, with inflows (energy, resources, services) and outflows (products, waste, energy). According to Common & Stagl (2015), this conception, which highlights the interdependence between the economy and the environment, is the starting point for Ecological economics. The economics curricula do not show the relevance of the numerous and fundamental

services provided by the ecosystem: provision of food and water, cultural and recreational services, genetic resources, pollination, regulation of climate and atmospheric composition, etc. (Costanza et al., 1997; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Last but not least, textbooks also ignore the importance of biodiversity for human well-being (Carpenter et al., 2006; Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2019; Jackson & Webster, 2016) and the way and extent to which well-being is reduced as a consequence of the deterioration of natural resources by economic activities.

Economic growth remains the dominant paradigm (Schmelzer, 2015), and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and per capita GDP are still the most relevant measures for evaluating economic performance and development, understanding income as an end and not as a means, and the nature only as a resource (Røpke, 2020). The concept of ‘weak sustainability’ contributes to strengthening the idea that technology and investment will be enough to offset the effects of environmental deterioration, because human capacity has no limits in replacing nature. This idea constraints the understanding of the scope and complexity of ecosystem functions, and promotes a false conception of human capacities to replace nature. On the other hand, leaving normative judgments and ethical attitudes out of the analysis leads to the neglect of a fundamental dimension of sustainability (Vucetich & Nelson, 2010), since it is not possible to explain or evaluate it without considering 'the values' involved (Putnam, 2002). The notion of *Homo economicus* represents a simplification of the motivations and values of people, who are not considered as actors or social beings, but as independent entities whose main purpose is utility or profit maximisation (Bowles & Carlin, 2020; Sen, 2003). “The self-interest view of rationality involves *inter alia* a firm rejection of the ‘ethics-related’ view of motivation” (Sen 2003, 15). From this perspective, several aspects are overlooked: the long term, the rights and opportunities of future generations, and the moral obligations with respect to people and other beings in the present and future. **For instance, due to all these limitations, a tool of economic analysis such as externalities, widely used to examine negative environmental effects, such as pollution, fails to be an adequate concept or framework for understanding or considering sustainability. This is mainly due to the fact that externalities do not apply a concept of justice in line with sustainability (Baumgärtner & Quaas, 2010a, 2010b; Bithas, 2011; Common, 2011).** For all these reasons, the current teaching of economics at Bachillerato comes into conflict with the acquisition of the key competencies for sustainability, as it does not promote

collaboration, systemic vision and critical thinking, or the reflection on ethical attitudes in economic decision-making.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Even though the term ‘sustainability’ has been incorporated into teaching, especially since the approval of the 2030 Agenda’s SDGs, our findings suggest that the conception of ES being taught in economics courses in Spanish upper secondary has not been significantly altered. **ES, together with SD, not only occupies a marginal position and receives very little attention, but is also addressed with superficiality and non-criticism. Furthermore,** curricula still include certain ideas that are in conflict with sustainability and ESD and contrary to the changes promoted by UNESCO. Among these conflicting ideas, two are particularly harmful because they provide an untrue vision of reality: the description of the economy as a closed system and the omission of the role of ecosystem services and resources in human well-being. This should change so that the curricula can adapt to the real world and for the economics teaching to also contribute to meeting the commitments on ESD.

It is puzzling that the conception of the economy as a closed system is still preserved in the current context of a serious environmental crisis. It is a way to define the object of study (the relationships to be analysed) that might have been convenient a century ago, when the impact of human activities on nature was still limited and the ecosystem resources and services were abundant. But arguing that the economy is a closed system in the 21st century cannot be justified for the sake of simplification. Nowadays, it is crucial to offer a response to the environmental emergency, especially when the intensive use of natural resources has been the key to economic growth, leading to the deterioration of ecosystems and the loss of biodiversity. Comprehending that the planet’s resources are limited and that there are limits to growth is a necessary foundation for understanding SE. However, the oxymoron ‘sustainable economic growth’ is still widely used, as reflected in the use of the term even by the 2030 Agenda in SDG 8. There is also general scepticism about the existence of limits to growth and there is great confidence that technological progress, the functioning of markets and increased efficiency will make it possible to overcome the scarcity of resources and other limitations imposed by nature. Our findings suggest that the teaching of economics in Spanish upper secondary does not analyse how

economy interacts with nature, nor does it consider the interaction of society with nature or the underlying ethical attitudes. Undoubtedly, sustainability and SD are concepts where ‘facts’ are entangled with ‘values’ and ethical attitudes. The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005) offers no doubts about the dependence of the constituents of human well-being (health, security, basic material for a good life, good social relations, and freedom of choice and action) on ecosystem services. One of its main conclusions is that many ecosystem services have deteriorated and this compromises the well-being of future generations. However, from the teaching of economics, well-being is mostly related to the material component (GDP) but not to the services of nature. This approach has negative consequences because, as indicated by Stiglitz et al. (2009), what we measure affects what we do: what we do not measure remains hidden and decisions can be wrong.

Apparently, the curricula and textbooks have not been sufficiently adapted to the commitments undertaken by UNESCO (2005, 2017) to review teaching plans in order to achieve the goals of ESD. Sustainability is not integrated in a cross-sectional way, it does not have a basic character or special place, nor is the acquisition of key competencies for sustainability facilitated. In the case of the subject of economics in Bachillerato, the environment and sustainability are addressed in one section of the last content block, under the heading *Economic imbalances*. The subject of business economics pays even less attention to environmental issues.

Implementing the pedagogical changes necessary for an evolution in teaching and learning in the sense indicated by UNESCO (2017) remains a pending task in Spain. The difficulties in translating these approaches into the teaching practice have been acknowledged (Kostoulas-Makrakis, 2010). The construction of action-oriented knowledge on sustainability, with the capacity to change the vision of students and society, requires systemic thinking and critical reflection, and must not avoid the questions to which we do not know the answers. In this respect, we need to take into account the serious dilemma posed by commercial fishing or meat consumption (Morell, 2015), together with the energy and digital transition, since it demands an intensive use of mining resources and rare metals (Pitron, 2021). Critical understanding and evaluation of ethical attitudes towards sustainability, based on participatory, interactive and reflective learning, are key factors to achieve transformative learning. “Understanding

your own values, the values of the society you live in, and the values of others around the world is a central part of educating for a sustainable future” (UNESCO, 2005, 6).

The teaching of economics must be adapted to the changes in the conception of learning and modify its teaching contents. In this sense, we believe that economic textbooks should explain how the economy, and society, relate to nature (discarding the traditional view of the economy as a closed system). Textbooks should integrate the environment and sustainability in an intersectional way, which does not imply doing so in all lessons but doing it when describing basic concepts such as consumption, economic growth, **international trade**, and human well-being. And this learning should consider motivational pluralism, ethical attitudes and promote collaboration, systemic vision and critical thinking in economic decision-making in order to promote specific key competencies.

This poses a challenge to the economics departments of high schools and requires the commitment and training of teachers. The persistence of certain concepts and visions hinders, and sometimes prevents, the understanding of sustainability and the development of key competencies for SD. ESD must be holistic, contextual, and social (UNESCO, 2017). But the teaching of economics is not holistic or critical, nor does it adequately consider the difficulties of SD or the relationships with nature and society. Although the acquisition of knowledge is not enough to achieve sustainability, it is necessary to acquire the appropriate knowledge to properly understand how the world works and to acquire the meanings and skills necessary for sustainability. The aim of environmental education is, according to Jensen & Schnack (1997, 164), “to make students capable of envisioning alternative ways of development and to be able to participate in acting according to these objectives.” Given the notable shortcomings in economics teaching, there is no reason to think that it can contribute to building action-oriented knowledge on SD.

According to Bonnett (2017), education concerns the existence of people in the world, so it is inevitably environmental. The presence of the environment in economics education must not only increase but also change. Some of the contents and approaches do not agree with ES, since they teach a conception of the economy and the society as entities independent of nature, and reinforce the idea of natural resources as products, overlooking the vital functions that ecosystems provide and their intrinsic value. **Additionally, economics curricula revolve around a remarkably anthropocentric and misinformed**

conception of ethical attitudes (Bonnett, 2019; Bowles and Carlin, 2020; Dasgupta, 2021; Green, 2013). Seemingly, the epistemological rigidity of mainstream economics is a great obstacle to the adaptation of the teaching of economics. Nevertheless, these difficulties can be overcome, as shown by the project Curriculum Open-Access Resources in Economics (CORE Team, 2017), which leans towards more sensitive approaches regarding motivational pluralism, equity and ES than neoclassical economics.

So where should this research move next? Jimenez et al. (2017) emphasises that “textbooks remain a central classroom tool in most countries worldwide” and makes an interesting proposal to develop global monitoring and evaluation system of textbook content as “a useful approach to promote high quality education curricula worldwide” (Jimenez et al. 2017, 13). Indeed, broader and systemic analyses are necessary to assess the changes and identify the contradictions and deficiencies that persist with respect to SD in the curriculum and in the textbooks of the different subjects. This analysis has only been carried out for the subjects of economics and business economics in Spain but other subjects in upper secondary education may also require a revision of their contents. In particular of other key SD disciplines like biology and philosophy. According to Vucetich & Nelson (2010), comprehending sustainability requires measuring how society benefits from nature from the resources and services it gets from it (economy); analysing the state of nature and how it is affected by human activity (biology); and understanding our relationship with nature and with our fellow human beings and its consequences (philosophy). Ethics, as a reflection on moral action, is present in the philosophy curriculum. In order to advance in the formation of a shared vision leading to collective action, it would be advisable to focus this reflection on the study of human relationships with nature. This common vision must be complex and critical, capable of dealing with the profound changes, dilemmas and socio-environmental conflicts that sustainability transition implies. This collective insight must identify the instrumental and intrinsic values of nature and share moral obligations and normative criteria regarding nature and its conservation. The adequate integration of such diverse knowledge and skills in the framework of ESD is a difficult task that demands a significant effort of coordination and interdisciplinary approaches.

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